

Version1.2	4/14/2022 15:07:52 MST	Hartten and Khalsa (2022; https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6255666)
General conventions for "H-K Table Documentation and Metadata"		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google Sheets file names & paths in italics • Sheets within a workbook in "quotes" • Column headers indicated with [] • Documentation should be written so that a stranger can understand what's in the tables. Assume that after 6 months, you are a stranger! 		
Key sources for material in the H-K Table		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The current Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) can be found by going to https://wiki.esipfed.org/Attribute_Convention_for_Data_Discovery . • The current NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Conventions are at http://cfconventions.org (see the 'Latest Release' link on that page). The CF Conventions are designed to standardize metadata (in the form of 'attributes'), and sometimes the values those attributes can have. • The current CF Standard Names Table is at http://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-standard-names/current/build/cf-standard-name-table.html • The ISO/TC 211 standards for digital geographic information are available for purchase at https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html (ISO 19115-1:2014 Geographic information — Metadata — Part 1: Fundamentals). The North American Profile of ISO 19115-1 is available for no charge at https://www.fgdc.gov/standards/projects/incits-l1-standards-projects/NAP-Metadata/napMetadataProfileV101.pdf , and the schema for all the 191** standards are on GitHub at https://github.com/ISO-TC211/XML . Further information can be found at the Committee's website, https://committee.iso.org/home/tc211 . • Whenever possible, [Variable Names] in the H-K Table were taken from the CMIP6 MIP Tables. When that has not been possible, [Variable Names] were constructed in a similar fashion and style to CMIP6 variables. As of 22 February 2022, the <u>CMIP6 Participation Guidance for Modelers</u> (Karl E. Taylor, Paul J. Durack, Mark Elkington, Eric Guilyardi, David Hassell, Michael Lautenschlager and Martina Stockhause; 17 October 2018) is at https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/Guide/modelers.html . Section 4, 'Model output fields', contains a link to the CMIP6 Data Request (https://www.earthsystemcog.org/projects/wip/CMIP6DataRequest) which redirects to https://cmip6dr.github.io/Data_Request_Home/ .That 'CMIP6 Data Request' webpage lists 'Key documents describing the request (in the 'docs' directory of the repository)' The 'Spreadsheet view ...' contains a link to http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/svn/exarch/CMIP6dreq/tags/latest/dreqPy/docs/CMIP6_MIP_tables.xlsx ; the first sheet in the spreadsheet names it as Request Version = 01.00.32. 		
Usage notes		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If a [Variable Name] that is not in the H-K Table is required, it should be from CMIP, or else be constructed to be CMIP-like. To clearly identify the same variable observed or derived from different methods or platforms, an "_ext" construct can be used (e.g. _radar, _tower, _bulk, _platformN). 		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each [Variable Name] in the H-K Table is associated with [Canonical Units]. The variables do not have to be written in those units! Rather, they must be written in units that are physically equivalent to the canonical units, and the descriptor of those units (the 'units' attribute) must in general be contained in UNIDATA's Udunits package (UDUNITS, see https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/udunits/#). For more details, see §1.4 (Overview) and §3.1 (Units) in the CF Conventions. 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The list of [Attributes] in "Global Attributes" is not meant to be limiting. If including additional global attributes would help describe your data, please include them. 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The list of [Minimum recommended variable attributes ...] in "Observatory and Model Variables" is not meant to be limiting. Feel free to include additional attributes if they would help describe your data to users. 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When writing Global or Variable attributes, keep in mind that in order to improve readability in ncdump outputs the CF Conventions recommend embedding newline characters into long strings to break them into lines (http://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/cf-conventions.html#_attributes). 		
License		
<p>This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/.</p>		
Citation		
<p>Hartten, Leslie M., & Khalsa, Siri Jodha S. (2022). The H-K Variable SchemaTable developed for the YOPPSiteMIP (1.2). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6255667</p>		
end of H-K_Table Documentation (Instructions)		

Version1.2	4/14/2022 15:07:52 MST	Hartten and Khalsa (2022; https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6255666)
5-Aug-2021	<u>Initial documentation</u>	
This new Master workbook created 5-Aug-2021 by L.M. Hartten from the following:		
* Google workbook <i>Master Table of YOPPSiteMIP Variable Names and Variables</i> (created by L.M. Hartten, 5 Nov 2019).		
Only the following active, unlocked sheets were retained:		
- "Observatory and Model Variables", the current working version (editable by many; shared with a few more)		
- "Global Attributes"		
- "Documentation and Metadata"		
23-Sep-2021	<u>Summary of modifications by L.M. Hartten</u>	
• Renamed this to Hartten-Khalsa_Master_YOPPSiteMIP_VariableSchema		
• Restricted "Editing" to Holt & Khalsa, "Viewing" to Gallagher & Uttal, and removed all others, in preparation for publishing.		
• Edited "Global Attributes" in preparation for publication of the table		
- Removed [Comment] since all had been answered.		
• Edited "Observatory and Model Variables" in preparation for publication of the table		
- Deleted columns not relevant to MODF Makers.		
- Cleaned up formatting and some cell contents, in part for readability and to enable the PDF to fit on a landscape 8.5"x14" (U.S. Legal) sheet.		
- Revised comments about standard vs. gregorian calendar to reflect CF Metadata Conventions v1.9 (which deprecates 'gregorian')		
• Edited "H-K_Table Documentation and Metadata" for clarity and to reflect revisions		
1-Nov-2021	<u>Summary of modifications by L.M. Hartten</u>	
• Edited "Observatory and Model Variables"		
- Deleted obsolete notes, re-ordered some columns, and simplified column headers.		
- Added CMIP/CMIP-like info to explanatory note before 1st set of variables about using an _ext construct for same variable from different platforms/methods.		
• Edited "Global Attributes"		
- Re-ordered some columns and reworded a column header.		
• Edited "H-K_Table Documentation and Metadata"		
- Minor format/wording tweaks to improve readability when frozen into a H-K_Table* version		
22-Feb-2022	<u>Summary of modifications by L.M. Hartten</u>	
• Edited "Global Attributes"		
- Tweaked some Notes for clarity, and to bring CF Convention & Standard Name Table version up to date.		
• Reworked "H-K_Table Documentation and Metadata" sheet into two sheets:		
"H-K_Table Documentation (Instructions)" and "H-K_Table Documentation (Lineage)"		

- Reformatted content of "H-K_Table Documentation (Instructions)" to improve readability and utility.		
25-Feb-2022	<u>Summary of modifications by L.M. Hartten</u>	
• Edited "Observatory and Model Variables"		
- Added CF standard_name for mrlsl (long_name = Average layer soil moisture)		
13-Apr-2022	<u>Summary of modifications by L.M. Hartten</u>	
• Edited "H-K_Table Documentation (Instructions)"		
- Added subsections for _License_ and _Citation_		
• Edited "Observatory and Model Variables"		
- Added CMIP6 variable wa (standard_name= upward_air_velocity)		
- Changed relevance of rhos (standard_name= snow_density) to both MMDFs & MODFs		
- Edited description of orog and removed variables latr & lonr. Added a note to all of them regarding their usage for multi-site data or tiled/categorized model output.		

Version 1.2	4/14/2022 15:07:52 MST	Hartten and Khalsa (2022; https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6255666)		
Attribute (from ACDD, CF, or ISO/TC 211)	Description of required information	Notes	MMDF? MODF?	Development Phase
title	Short human-readable phrase or sentence describing the dataset		both	1
date_created	The date on which this version of the data was created (not considering changes to metadata)	ISO 8601 is preferred. "ACDD strongly encourages the use of the 'extended' format date-time, in the form YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss<zone> (although ss, mm, and hh can be omitted, and <zone> can be Z, ±hh:mm, or ±hh)."	both	1
Conventions	List of the conventions that are followed by the dataset	e.g. 'ACDD-1.3', 'CF-1.9', 'SVO-1.0.0', etc., separated either by blanks or by commas	both	1
standard_name_vocabulary	Name and version of the controlled vocabulary from which variable standard names are taken	e.g. 'CF Standard Name Table v78'	both	1
contributor_name	Responsible Party	e.g. the primary contact for the modelling or observational project	both	1
contributor_email	EEmail of Responsible Party		both	1
institution	Institution where the original data was produced.		both	1
creator_name	The name of the person responsible for creating this data		both	1
creator_email	EEmail of the person responsible for creating this data	Consider adding a second email, e.g. for the department's data team, that is unlikely to be affected by a person leaving the institution	both	1
project	Name of the project(s) principally responsible for originating this data	Multiple projects can be separated by commas. Suggest 'YOPP' and 'YOPPSiteMIP'.	both	1
source	The method of production of the original data. If it was model-generated, name the model and its version. If it is observational, characterize it.	Examples: 'CTD #1234'; 'world model v.0.1'. For MODFs, this information is probably better done as a variable attribute.	MMDF	1
summary	A paragraph describing the dataset	For readability in ncdump outputs it is recommended to embed newline characters into long strings to break them into separate lines.	both	1
history	Provides an audit trail for modifications to the original data.	CF Conventions recommend that each line begin with a timestamp indicating the date and time of day that modifications were made.	both	1
id	Persistent Identifier (PID) for dataset		both	1
naming_authority	Naming authority for PID (preferably using reverse-DNS naming, e.g. 'edu.ucar.unidata', although URIs may be used)		both	1
license	Terms of distribution and use	e.g. the URL to a standard or specific license; "Freely Distributed" or "None"; free-text description of restrictions to data access and distribution. Consider using Creative Commons licences 'CCO' or 'CC BY 4.0'.	both	1
metadata_link	URL to detailed documentation (DOIs expressed as http://doi.org/...)	DOI of a publication (e.g. an article in a data journal) is preferred, but a persistent URL is acceptable.	both	1
references	Published or web-based references that describe the data or methods used to produce it		both	1
time_coverage_start	The time of the first data point in the data set	ISO 8601 is preferred	MODF	1
time_coverage_end	The time of the last data point in the data set	ISO 8601 is preferred	MODF	1
keywords	Comma-separated list of key words and/or phrases, preferably drawn from a controlled vocabulary, e.g. the GCMD at https://earthdata.nasa.gov/earth-observation-data/find-data/gcmd/gcmd-keywords		both	1
featureType	One of the following, as of 15 Sept 2021: 'point', 'timeSeries', 'trajectory', 'profile', 'timeSeriesProfile', or 'trajectoryProfile' (see http://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-conventions/cf-conventions-1.9/cf-conventions.html#_features_and_feature_types)	Essential for the visualization tools that are being developed	both	1

Version 1.2		4/14/2022 15:07:52 MST		Hartten and Khalsa (2022; https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6255666)					
Temporal dimensions and variables									
Variable Name	long_name	standard_name	units	Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)	Notes	URI for variable definition	MMDF? MODF?	Development Phase	
time	Valid time	time	hours since ...	long_name; units; delta_t; standard_name; calendar	Use "calendar: standard" since "calendar: gregorian" is deprecated (CF-1.9).		MMDF	As needed	
time01	Valid time for observations with 1-minute cadence	time	hours since ...	long_name; units; delta_t; standard_name; calendar	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable. Use "calendar: standard" since "calendar: gregorian" is deprecated (CF-1.9).		MODF	As needed	
time05	Valid time for observations with 5-minute cadence	time	hours since ...	long_name; units; delta_t; standard_name; calendar	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable. Use "calendar: standard" since "calendar: gregorian" is deprecated (CF-1.9).		MODF	As needed	
time10	Valid time for observations with 10-minute cadence	time	hours since ...	long_name; units; delta_t; standard_name; calendar	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable. Use "calendar: standard" since "calendar: gregorian" is deprecated (CF-1.9).		MODF	As needed	
time15	Valid time for observations with 15-minute cadence	time	hours since ...	long_name; units; delta_t; standard_name; calendar	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable. Use "calendar: standard" since "calendar: gregorian" is deprecated (CF-1.9).		MODF	As needed	
time30	Valid time for observations with 30-minute cadence	time	hours since ...	long_name; units; delta_t; standard_name; calendar	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable. Use "calendar: standard" since "calendar: gregorian" is deprecated (CF-1.9).		MODF	As needed	
time60	Valid time for observations with 60-minute cadence	time	hours since ...	long_name; units; delta_t; standard_name; calendar	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable. Use "calendar: standard" since "calendar: gregorian" is deprecated (CF-1.9).		MODF	As needed	
time_sonde	Radiosonde valid time	time	hours since ...	long_name; units; standard_name; calendar	No CMIP name. Not a dimension, but a variable reported by some sondes. Use "calendar: standard" since "calendar: gregorian" is deprecated (CF-1.9).		MODF	As needed	
time_release_sonde	Radiosonde release time	time	hours since ...	long_name; units; standard_name; calendar	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable. Use "calendar: standard" since "calendar: gregorian" is deprecated (CF-1.9).		MODF	As needed	
release_time	Radiosonde release time in character form			long_name; cf_role	No CMIP name. CHAR(date_length,time_release_sonde).		MODF	As needed	
Spatial dimensions, and dimensions and variables not listed elsewhere									

<i>Variable Name</i>	<i>long_name</i>	<i>standard_name</i>	<i>units</i>	<i>Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)</i>	<i>Notes</i>	<i>URI for variable definition</i>	<i>MMDF? MODF?</i>	<i>Development Phase</i>
level	Integer index for primary model grid	model_level_number	1	long_name; units; standard_name			MMDF	1
half_level	Integer index for secondary (staggered) model grid	model_level_number	1	long_name; units; standard_name			MMDF	1
slevel	Depth of middle of soil layer	depth	m	long_name; units; standard_name	No CMIP name.		MMDF	1
height_tower	Tower observation height	height	m	long_name; units; standard_name	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable. Use only for variables measured at all levels; otherwise use a sizeN dimension and a comment to define the N heights.		MODF	1
height_radar	Radar observation height	height	m	long_name; units; standard_name	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable.		MODF	As needed
lat_sonde	Radiosonde latitude	latitude	degrees_north	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source	No CMIP name. Not a dimension, but a variable measured by some sondes.		MODF	1
lon_sonde	Radiosonde longitude	longitude	degrees_east	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source	No CMIP name. Not a dimension, but a variable measured by some sondes.		MODF	1
alt_sonde	Radiosonde altitude	altitude	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source	No CMIP name. Not a dimension, but a variable measured by some sondes.		MODF	1
zg_sonde	Radiosonde geopotential height	geopotential_height	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source	No CMIP name. Not a dimension, but a variable measured by some sondes.		MODF	1
depth_soilprobe	Soil observation depth	depth	m	long_name; units; standard_name	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable.		MODF	4
depth_iceprobe	Ice observation depth	depth	m	long_name; units; standard_name	No CMIP name. A dimension and a variable.		MODF	4
sample	Index (instance dimension) of radiosonde observations in file		1	long_name	No CMIP name. Formerly called "obs". A dimension but not a variable.		MODF	1
count_per_sonde	Number of samples for this radiosonde		1	long_name; sample_dimension	No CMIP name		MODF	1
index_sonde	Index of the first sample for this radiosonde		1	long_name; sample_dimension	No CMIP name		MODF	1
source_sonde	Source of radiosonde data in character form			long_name	No CMIP name. CHAR(flag_length, time_release_sonde), used when sondes launched by different organizations are combined in the data record.		MODF	1

source_length	First dimension (number of characters) of source_sonde			long_name	No CMIP name. A dimension but not a variable, used when sondes launched by different organizations are combined in the data record.		MODF	1
date_length	First dimension (number of characters) of release_time			long_name	No CMIP name. A dimension but not a variable.		MODF	1
Single-level fixed variables								
Variable Name	long_name	standard_name	units	Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)	Notes	URI for variable definition	MMDF? MODF?	Development Phase
sftlf	Land area fraction	land_area_fraction	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent". If applicable, provide information on tiles, and how they are populated for the main model output and the surrounding locations. For each tile provide information on what type of soil and vegetation.		MMDF	1
orog	Surface altitude	surface_altitude	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; source; references; comment	Provide information for the main grid output or station as well as for the surrounding locations. The surface called "surface" means the lower boundary of the atmosphere. Altitude is the (geometric) height above the geoid, which is the reference geopotential surface. The geoid is similar to mean sea level.		both	1
lat	Latitude	latitude	degrees_north	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; source; references; comment	For Supersites or installations with multiple locations, a sub-site dimension should be used; the most representative location should be stored under the first index and others under subsequent indices.		both	1
lon	Longitude	longitude	degrees_east	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; source; references; comment	For Supersites or installations with multiple locations, a sub-site dimension should be used; the most representative location should be stored under the first index and others under subsequent indices.		both	1
Single-level atmospheric variables								
Variable Name	long_name	standard_name	units	Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)	Notes	URI for variable definition	MMDF? MODF?	Development Phase
z0m	Surface roughness for momentum	surface_roughness_length_for_momentum_in_air	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	No CMIP name		both	2

z0h	Surface roughness for heat	surface_roughness_length_for_heat_in_air	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	No CMIP name. If a different value is used for moisture, please provide that as z0q		both	2
psl	Mean sea level pressure	air_pressure_at_mean_sea_level	Pa	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	1
ps	Surface pressure	surface_air_pressure	Pa	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	1
uas	Near-surface (10m) eastward wind	eastward_wind	m s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	1
vas	Near-surface (10m) northward wind	northward_wind	m s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	1

zmla	Height of atmospheric boundary layer	atmosphere_boundary_layer_thickness	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Provide description on how it is calculated		both	2
tas	Near-surface (2m) air temperature	air_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	1
tdps	Near-surface (2m) dew point temperature	dew_point_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	1
huss	Near-surface (2m) specific humidity	specific_humidity	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "kg kg-1".		both	1
hurs	Near-surface (2m) relative humidity	relative_humidity	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent".		both	1

pr	Total precipitation of water in all phases per unit area	precipitation_flux	kg m-2 s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	At surface, both liquid and solid		both	1
clt	Total cloud cover	cloud_area_fraction	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent".		both	3
cod	Cloud optical thickness	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_cloud	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	3
prw	Total column water vapour	atmosphere_mass_content_of_water_vapor	kg m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Also known as precipitable water vapor		both	1
clwvi	Total column cloud water in liquid phase	atmosphere_mass_content_of_cloud_liquid_water	kg m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Also known as liquid water path		both	3

clivi	Total column icewater	atmosphere_mass_content_of_cloud_ice	kg m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Also known as ice water path		both	3
visas	Surface horizontal visibility	visibility_in_air	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	No CMIP name		MODF	1
oz	Ozone concentration in air	mole_fraction_of_ozone_in_air	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "1e-9".		both	3
Surface and TOA variables								
Variable Name	long_name	standard_name	units	Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)	Notes	URI for variable definition	MMDF? MODF?	Development Phase
snd	Surface snow thickness	surface_snow_thickness	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
snc	Surface snow area fraction	surface_snow_area_fraction	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent".		MMDF	2

snw	Snow water equivalent	liquid_water_content_of_surface_snow	kg m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
ts	Surface (skin) temperature where land or sea ice	surface_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	2
tsns	Snow surface skin temperature	surface_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	2
tsn	Snow temperature	temperature_in_surface_snow	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Provide vertical grid if more than one layer (as snowlevel)		both	4
rhos	Snow density	snow_density	kg m-3	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	No CMIP name. Provide vertical grid if more than one layer		both	4
cnc	Canopy area fraction	vegetation_area_fraction	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent".		MMDF	2

tgs	Ground skin temperature	surface_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	2
rlut	Top-of-atmosphere outgoing long wave radiation	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Follow the CMIP convention that outgoing fluxes are positive upward. The TOA outgoing longwave flux is the upwelling thermal radiative flux, often called the "outgoing longwave radiation" or "OLR".		MMDF	3
rsdt	Top-of-atmosphere incoming short-wave radiation	toa_incoming_shortwave_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Follow the CMIP convention that incoming fluxes are positive downward. The TOA incoming shortwave flux is the radiative flux from the sun i.e. the "downwelling" TOA shortwave flux.		MMDF	3
rsut	Top-of-atmosphere outgoing short-wave radiation	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Follow the CMIP convention that outgoing fluxes are positive upward. The TOA outgoing shortwave flux is the reflected and scattered solar radiative flux i.e. the "upwelling" TOA shortwave flux, sometimes called the "outgoing shortwave radiation" or "OSR".		MMDF	3
rsus	Upward surface short-wave radiation	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upwelling fluxes are positive upward		both	2
rsds	Downward short-wave radiation at the surface	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that downwelling fluxes are positive downward		both	2

rlus	Upward surface long-wave radiation	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upwelling fluxes are positive upward		both	2
rlds	Downward surface long-wave radiation	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that downwelling fluxes are positive downward		both	2
hfls	Surface turbulent latent heat flux	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward		MMDF	2
hfls_bulk	Surface turbulent latent heat flux (bulk method)	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward		MODF	2
hfls_ec	Surface turbulent latent heat flux (eddy covariance method)	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward		MODF	2
hfss	Surface turbulent sensible heat flux	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward		MMDF	2

hfss_bulk	Surface turbulent sensible heat flux (bulk method)	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward		MODF	2
hfss_ec	Surface turbulent sensible heat flux (eddy covariance method)	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward		MODF	2
hfds	Ground heat flux	downward_heat_flux_at_ground_level_in_soil	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF/CMIP convention that flux from the atmosphere into the ground is positive downward		both	2
hfdsn	Surface downward heat flux in snow	surface_downward_heat_flux_in_snow	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	The surface called "surface" means the lower boundary of the atmosphere. Follow the CF/CMIP convention that flux from the atmosphere into the snow is positive downward		both	4
hfdsnb	Downward heat flux at snow botton	downward_heat_flux_at_ground_level_in_snow	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF/CMIP convention that flux from the snow into the ice or land under the snow is positive downward		both	4

albs	Surface albedo	surface_albedo	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	2
albsn	Snow albedo	surface_albedo	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Albedo over snowcovered portion of gridcell		both	2
tauu	Time-average eastward turbulent surface stress	surface_downward_eastward_stress	Pa	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "N m-2".		both	2
tauv	Time-average northward turbulent surface stress	surface_downward_northward_stress	Pa	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "N m-2".		both	2
Atmospheric variables on model or instrument levels								
Variable Name	long_name	standard_name	units	Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)	Notes	URI for variable definition	MMDF? MODF?	Development Phase
zg	Geopotential height	geopotential_height	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Provide for both full and half levels if applicable		MMDF	1
zghalf	Geopotential height on half levels	geopotential_height	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			MMDF	1

pfull	Pressure on full levels	air_pressure	Pa	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range		M MDF	1
phalf	Pressure on half levels	air_pressure	Pa	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range		M MDF	1
pa	Atmospheric pressure	air_pressure	Pa	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment		both	1
ua	Eastward wind component	eastward_wind	m s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment		both	1
va	Northward wind component	northward_wind	m s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment		both	1
wa	Vertical velocity	upward_air_velocity	m s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment		both	1
wap	Vertical large-scale wind in pressure coordinates	lagrangian_tendency_of_air_pressure	Pa s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Omega, positive downwards	M MDF	1

ta	Temperature	air_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	1
tdp	Dew-point temperature	dew_point_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	1
hus	Specific humidity	specific_humidity	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "kg kg-1"		both	1
hur	Relative humidity	relative_humidity	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent".		both	1
thetawb	Wet-bulb potential temperature	wet_bulb_potential_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	1
tnt	Tendency of air temperature	tendency_of_air_temperature	K s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			MMDF	1

tna	Tendency of air temperature due to advection	tendency_of_air_temperature_due_to_advection	K s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			M MDF	1
tnus	Tendency of specific humidity	tendency_of_specific_humidity	s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			M MDF	1
tnusa	Tendency of specific humidity due to advection	tendency_of_specific_humidity_due_to_advection	s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			M MDF	1
tnua	Tendency of eastward wind	tendency_of_eastward_wind	m s-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			M MDF	1
tnva	Tendency of northward wind	tendency_of_northward_wind	m s-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			M MDF	1
rlu	Upward short-wave radiation	upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upwelling fluxes are positive upward		both	2
rld	Downward short-wave radiation	downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that downwelling fluxes are positive downward		both	2
rsu	Upward long-wave radiation	upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upwelling fluxes are positive upward		both	2

rsd	Downward long-wave radiation	downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that downwelling fluxes are positive downward		both	2
evu	Vertical eddy diffusivity coefficient for momentum due to parameterized turbulence	atmosphere_momentum_diffusivity	m2 s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			MMDF	2
edt	Vertical eddy diffusion coefficient for temperature due to parameterized turbulence	atmosphere_heat_diffusivity	m2 s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			MMDF	2
wthv	Turbulent sensible heat flux based on virtual potential temperature	upward_sensible_heat_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	GCSS variable name. Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward.		both	2
wqv	Turbulent moisture flux based on vapor content	upward_latent_heat_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	GCSS variable name. Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward.		both	2
uw	Eastward turbulent momentum flux	downward_eastward_momentum_flux_in_air	kg m-1 s-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	GCSS variable name. Follow the CF convention that downward fluxes are positive downward.		both	2

vw	Northward turbulent momentum flux	downward_northward_momentum_flux_in_air	kg m-1 s-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	GCSS variable name. Follow the CF convention that downward fluxes are positive downward.		both	2
tke	Turbulent kinetic energy	kinetic_energy_content_of_atmosphere_layer	J m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	GCSS variable name		both	2
cl	Percentage cloud cover, including both large-scale and convective cloud	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent".		MMDF	3
clw	Mass fraction of cloud liquid water	mass_fraction_of_cloud_liquid_water_in_air	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Canonical unit can alternatively be "kg kg-1"		MMDF	3
cli	Mass fraction of cloud ice	mass_fraction_of_cloud_ice_in_air	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Canonical unit can alternatively be "kg kg-1"		MMDF	3
prsn	Snowfall flux per unit area	snowfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	All precipitation in solid phase. If only one level is available, the flux should be provided together with metadata identifying the level.		both	3
Sub-surface terrestrial variables								
Variable Name	long_name	standard_name	units	Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)	Notes	URI for variable definition	MMDF? MODF?	Development Phase

tsl	Bulk soil temperature	soil_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Provide vertical grid if more than one layer (as soillevel)		both	4
mrlsl	Average layer soil moisture	moisture_content_of_soil_layer	kg m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Provide vertical grid if more than one layer		both	4
Fixed ocean variables for ocean locations only, reported on atmospheric grid								
CMIP Variable name (or CMIP-like)	long_name (netCDF)	standard_name (CF)	Canonical Unit	Minimum recommended variable attributes for MMDFs (if applicable) & MODFs	Notes	URI for variable definition	MMDF? MODF?	Development Phase
thkcello	Ocean model cell thickness	cell_thickness	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			MMDF	4
Ocean variables on model or instrument levels								
Variable Name	long_name	standard_name	units	Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)	Notes	URI for variable definition	MMDF? MODF?	Development Phase
to	Ocean temperature	sea_water_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
so	Sea water salinity	sea_water_salinity	1e-3	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	The units of salinity are dimensionless and the units attribute should normally be given as 1e-3 or 0.001 i.e. parts per thousand.		both	4

uo	Ocean u-velocity	eastward_sea_water_velocity	m s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
vo	Ocean v-velocity	northward_sea_water_velocity	m s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
wo	Ocean w-velocity	upward_sea_water_velocity	m s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
Ocean single level variables								
Variable Name	long_name	standard_name	units	Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)	Notes	URI for variable definition	M MDF? MODF?	Development Phase
tos	Sea surface temperature	sea_surface_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4

mlotst	Ocean mixed-layer depth	ocean_mixed_layer_thickness	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	If defined by sigma T, use ocean_mixed_layer_thickness_defined_by_sigma_t		both	4
hfsso	Atmosphere-ocean sensible heat flux	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward.		both	4
hflso	Atmosphere-ocean latent heat flux	surface_downward_latent_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that downward fluxes are positive downward.		both	4
rsntds	Net downward shortwave radiation at sea water surface	net_downward_shortwave_flux_at_sea_water_surface	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that downward fluxes are positive downward.		both	4
rlntds	Net downward longwave radiation at sea water surface	surface_net_downward_longwave_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that downward fluxes are positive downward.		both	4

wfo	Fresh water flux into sea water	water_flux_into_sea_water	kg m-2 s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	"Water" means water in all phases, including frozen. "Downward" indicates a vector component which is positive when directed downward. The surface water flux is the result of precipitation and evaporation. The water flux into sea water is the freshwater entering as a result of precipitation, evaporation, river inflow, sea ice effects and water flux correction (if applied). "River" refers to water in the fluvial system (stream and floodplain).		both	4
fsitherm	Water flux into sea water due to sea ice thermodynamic	water_flux_into_sea_water_due_to_surface_drainage	kg m-2 s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	The water flux into the ocean is the freshwater entering the sea water as a result of precipitation, evaporation, river inflow, sea ice effects and water flux correction (if applied). "Surface drainage" refers to all melt water forming at the sea ice surface and subsequently running into the sea.		MMDF	4
tauuo	Ocean surface x-stress	surface_downward_eastward_stress	Pa	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "N m-2". Surface downward x Stress		both	4
tauvo	Ocean surface y-stress	surface_downward_northward_stress	Pa	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "N m-2". Surface downward y Stress		both	4
sigwave	Significant wave height	sea_surface_wave_significant_height	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	No CMIP name		both	4
<p>Sea ice variables, reported on atmospheric grid; Quantities refer to the ice-covered fraction portion of the grid-cell only</p>								

<i>Variable Name</i>	<i>long_name</i>	<i>standard_name</i>	<i>units</i>	<i>Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)</i>	<i>Notes</i>	<i>URI for variable definition</i>	<i>MMDF? MODF?</i>	<i>Development Phase</i>
siconc	Sea-ice concentration (area fraction)	sea_ice_area_fraction	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent". Only report variables if siconc > 0		both	4
siitdconc	Sea-ice concentration (area fraction) in categories	sea_ice_area_fraction	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent".		MMDF	4
sithick	Sea-ice thickness	sea_ice_thickness	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
siitdthick	Sea-ice thickness in thickness categories	sea_ice_thickness	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			MMDF	4
sisnthick	Snow thickness on sea ice	surface_snow_thickness	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
siage	Sea-ice age	age_of_sea_ice	year	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range	Canonical unit can alternatively be "s".		MMDF	4

siu	Sea-ice u-velocity	eastward_sea_ice_velocity	m s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
siv	Sea-ice v-velocity	northward_sea_ice_velocity	m s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
sisali	Sea-ice salinity	sea_ice_salinity	1e-3	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			MODF	4
sistresave	Sea-ice normal stress (pressure)	sea_ice_average_normal_horizontal_stress	N m-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			MMDF	4
sicompstren	Compressive sea-ice strength	compressive_strength_of_sea_ice	Pa m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range			MMDF	4
sitemptop	Sea-ice surface temperature (at the interface of sea ice and the overlying air or snow)	sea_ice_surface_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4

sitempsnic	Temperature at snow-ice interface	sea_ice_surface_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
sitempbot	Temperature at ice-ocean interface	sea_ice_basal_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
sialb	Sea-ice / snow albedo	sea_ice_albedo	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent".		both	2
siflsensupbot	Ocean-ice net sensible heat flux	upward_sea_ice_basal_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward.		both	2
siflsenstop	Net upward sensible heat flux over sea ice	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward.. Specify surface type with mask=siconc		both	2

sifflatstop	Net upward latent heat flux over sea ice	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upward fluxes are positive upward.. Specify surface type with mask=siconc		both	2
siflswdtop	Downwelling shortwave flux over sea ice	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that downwelling fluxes are positive downward. Specify surface type with mask=siconc		both	2
siflswutop	Upwelling shortwave flux over sea ice	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upwelling fluxes are positive upward. Specify surface type with mask=siconc		both	2
sifllwdtop	Downwelling longwave flux over sea ice	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that downwelling fluxes are positive downward. Specify surface type with mask=siconc		both	2
sifllwutop	Upwelling longwave flux over sea ice	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that upwelling fluxes are positive upward. Specify surface type with mask=siconc		both	2

siflcondtop	Net conductive heat flux in ice at the surface	surface_downward_sensible_heat_flux	W m-2	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Follow the CF convention that downward fluxes are positive downward.		both	2
sipr	Rainfall rate over sea ice	rainfall_flux	kg m-2 s-1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4
ficonc	Fast ice concentration (area fraction)	sea_ice_area_fraction	1	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	Canonical unit can alternatively be "percent". No CMIP name; specify ice type with CF variable sea_ice_classification		both	4
fithick	Fast ice thickness	sea_ice_thickness	m	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment	No CMIP name; specify ice type with CF variable sea_ice_classification		both	4
Sea ice variables, reported on sea-ice model grid; Quantities refer to the ice-covered fraction portion of the grid-cell only								

<i>Variable Name</i>	<i>long_name</i>	<i>standard_name</i>	<i>units</i>	<i>Minimum recommended variable attributes (if applicable)</i>	<i>Notes</i>	<i>URI for variable definition</i>	<i>MMDF? MODF?</i>	<i>Development Phase</i>
sitemp	Temperature within sea ice	sea_ice_temperature	K	long_name; units; standard_name; missing_value; actual_range; instrument; source; references; history; original_name; contributor_name; contributor_email; creator_name; creator_email; institution; comment			both	4